

Data Management Plan 1

Deliverable 1.2

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Data Management Plan 1

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DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

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1. Definitions and acronyms

Table 1

Acronym	Definition
CC	Creative Commons
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council
DataCite Metadata Schema	List of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, along with recommended use instructions.
Dataset	A grouping of data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Dublin Core	The Dublin Core Metadata Element Set is one of the simplest and most widely used metadata schema.
EDR	Endpoint Detection and Response
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems
IPTP	Field Crops Institute, (Chirpan, Bulgaria)
ITC tool	Information Communication Technology tool
Metadata	A description for data
Metadata schema	A metadata schema establishes and defines data elements and the rules governing the use of data elements to describe a resource
OFC	OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose
OpenAIRE	A European project supporting Open Science.
Re3data	A global registry of research data repositories that covers research data repositories from different academic disciplines

Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RKH	Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hubs
SACO platform	It is the Shared Storage Service of the CSIC (Spanish institution of which the OH-FINE coordinating team is a member) that allows files to be stored and shared easily.
SGGW	Warsaw University of Life Sciences (Poland)
WP	Work package

Table 1. Abbreviations and terminology used in the document

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2. Introduction

The scope of the first version of the OH-FINE Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used throughout the project. The DMP will ensure that this data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), according to the guidelines provided by the Regulation (EU) 2021/695 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation and the data management requirements under Article 17 of the Grant Agreement (GA).

The DMP is a living document that describes the data management starting from its collection, including its processing and handling during OH-FINE and, finally, its later archiving and dissemination. Upcoming versions of this DMP will cover changes to the specifications provided or incorporations (new sets of data not contemplated earlier) occurred along the life of the project.

2.1 Project Background

Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe –OH-FINE– has a duration of 48 months, starting from the 1st of November 2024, and is funded by the European Union in the framework of Horizon Europe, the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme 2021-2027, and by SERI, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation. The project is coordinated by the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiological Sciences of Salamanca (IRNASA), which is part of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The project focusses on empowering European farmers by advancing and sharing sustainable organic farming knowledge and solutions that align with farmer capabilities, consumer demands, and evolving food market trends. The project involves 18 partners from 9 countries.

2.2 Data Management Plan objectives

The Deliverable 1.2 “Data Management Plan 1” is part of the work package 1 “Project Management”, led by CSIC and is aligned with FAIR data management guidelines. Its objective is to outline the methodology for data collection, complementary sources, standards, personal data protection, storage, preservation, access rights and reuse.

This deliverable will be accompanied by Deliverable 1.1 “Project Management Plan 1” (Dissemination Level: Sensitive), developed by CSIC and submitted by month 5 (March

2025) and the Deliverable 1.3 “Legal and Ethical report” (Dissemination Level: Sensitive), developed by EURADIA-BETANIA that will be submitted in month 6 (April 2025). The data management guidelines are aligned with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) No 2016/679) and electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services (eIDAS, Regulation (EU) No 910/2014) European regulations.

An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released if other types of data are generated/collected, if there are changes in the consortium's policies or composition, and if any other external factors affect the validity of the current DMP. Deliverable 1.5 “Data Management Plan 2” will include all these updates and it will be submitted in month 17 (March 2026).

3. Data summary

3.1 The purpose of the data collection/generation in OH-FINE and the relation to the objectives of the project

The scope of the data collection and generation in OH-FINE is to provide solid knowledge and scientific evidence to support European organic farmers, to create a pan-European Organic Farming Learning Community and to issue guidelines and policy recommendations that foster the conversion to organic production. In order to avoid duplication or overlap with other initiatives, existing information (published in repositories, scientific literature and platforms specialized in organic production) will be reused.

New knowledge derived from project activities will also be generated. These data are detailed in the following section.

3.2 From raw data to final documents

The OH-FINE project comprises a multitude of activities including research, dissemination and collection of existing resources. As a consequence, different data types will be collected and generated. Figure 1 summarises the process, from raw data (new and reused) to the expected results of the project (final documents).

Figure 1. Description and type of data by degree of processing

3.3 Project datasets

A data set, in the context of open science, refers to a structured collection of data that can include both open and sensitive or confidential information. It is typically organized in a way that allows researchers to analyse, interpret, and share findings.

As shown in Figure 1, in OH-FINE project the raw data includes new data used to:

- The proper internal management of the project,
- Ensure data protection
- Be used as supporting information in other WP
- Obtain the expected results of the project (final documents) after the elaboration and processing of these new data as well as of data reused in the project.

These new data generated could be public or confidential. Confidential data contains personal or sensitive information, such as:

- Personal data (for members of consortium, producers participating in the hubs and those attending the activities)
- Data from surveys, interviews and case studies
- Data related to internal project management
- Analytical data from websites and social media

On the other hand, public data include:

- Experimental data from field trials
- In addition to scientific datasets, all other data that is considered relevant and may be useful for reuse by other stakeholders will be made public, provided that it complies with the GDPR (confidential data used will be anonymised or encrypted)

Table 2 summarizes the different dataset expected to be generated (new raw data) during the project in each of the work packages. These data will be used for the elaboration of different technical and dissemination documents that are expected to be generated as a result of the project (scientific papers, practice abstracts, deliverables, videos, technical documents, guides, policy briefs, etc.). This table will be updated in subsequent versions of the DMP as data sets are generated that are not currently foreseen.

As previously mentioned, many new data will be used as supporting information in other WP. To avoid redundancy, the table only includes new datasets in the WP in which they are generated for the first time, regardless of whether they are later reused as supporting information in other WPs.

Information about where the data will be stored and made available outside the project will be provided in section 4 (FAIR Data).

Table 2

Dataset related to	Description	Public (P) /Confidential (C)	Institution in charge
WP1. Project Management	Partner contact details	C	CSIC
	Internal management data	C	
	Project meetings materials (minutes, agendas...)	C	
WP2. Project set up, needs assessment and baseline establishment to inform subsequent WPs	Personal information producers (and their farms) selected for the 100 case study farms	C	TEAGASC
	Data from surveys, interviews and social network mapping exercises	C	
WP3. OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community – OFC	Database on stakeholders and knowledge entities relevant to organic agriculture	P	EV-ILVO
	Data about participants in the forums	C	
	Internal data for the management and organization of the forums,	C	
	Information gathered through data collection instruments in the forums, RKH and OFC	C	
WP4. OH-FINE Platform ITC tool	Decision Support System (Algorithm outputs, modelling data, risk assessments, scenario simulations)	C	EURADIA-BETANIA
	Market & Supply Chain Data	C	
	User Interaction & Engagement Data	C	
WP5. Training, capacity building, creation of information material and cross-fertilisation in the conversion to organic farming period	Participants in the activities (workshops, cross-visits, technical advisors visits, etc.)	C	SEAE
	Internal data for the management and organization of the activities (including consent forms for image use)	C	
	Information gathered through data collection instruments in the WP5 activities (training, cross visits, workshops, etc.)	C	

WP6. Training, capacity building, creation of information material and cross-fertilisation in the post-conversion to organic farming period	Participants in the activities (workshops, cross-visits, technical advisors visits, etc.)	C	BIOSELENA
	Internal data for the management and organization of the activities (including consent forms for image use)	C	
	Information gathered through data collection instruments in the WP6 activities (training, cross visits, workshops, etc.)	C	
WP7. Agricultural field trials	Data gathered during the design of experimental trials within a co-creative process	P	EV-ILVO
	Measures carried on the experimental trials (raw data)	P	
	Participants in the field demonstrations	C	
	Information gathered through data collection instruments in the field demonstration.	C	
WP8. Impact assessment during conversion to organic farming	Data from surveys, interviews and case studies	C	TEAGASC
WP9. Impact assessment during post-conversion period	Data from surveys, interviews and case studies	C	OFISET
WP10, WP11, WP12. Sustainability, communication and Dissemination of results	Monitoring data on the impact of communication and dissemination activities	C	SEAE / FiBL-CH
	Internal management data in the preparation of the material	C	
	Data on subscribers to the website	C	
	Analytical data from visitors of the project website	C	
	Analytical data collected by social media channels	C	

Table 2. Main dataset expected to be generated during the course of the OH-FINE project

3.4 Formats of data generated/collected

The OH-FINE project comprises a multitude of activities including research, dissemination and collection of existing resources. As a consequence, different data types will be collected and generated: datasets, surveys, images, sound and video recording, reports, presentations, press articles, etc.

The main types of data expected to be collected are described below. This list and its formats will be updated in subsequent versions of the DMP.

Data formats (table 3) should be selected with the view to facilitate data storage and transfer. To facilitate the raw data exchange, MS Excel compatible files including comma separated CSV and .xls(x) format will be used. For editable documents mainly .docx will be used and .pdf for definitive documents. Images and illustrations will be stored as .jpeg, .tiffs, .png, etc. Sound and video recording will be stored as .mp4, .mp3 or .wav.

Table 3

Type	Format
Structured data, raw datasets	.csv; .xlsx, .json, .sql
Editable documents	.docx, .txt
GIS/mapping data	.shp, geojson
Presentations	.pptx
Definitive documents and presentations	.pdf
Images, diagrams and illustrations	.jpeg, .tiffs, .png
Sound and video recording, multimedia content	.mp4, mp3, .wav

Table 3. Type and format of data expected to be generated in the OH-FINE project

3.5 If existing data is being reused

As it is very important to avoid redundancy with other initiatives, collaboration with other projects will be explored, especially EIP-Agri Operational Groups and other Horizon Europe projects (HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20, HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1, and HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3). Specific methods will be developed to prevent the duplication of efforts observed in other projects and networks. Reviews of agricultural and project repositories such as CORDIS, EU-Farm Book and Organic Farm Knowledge will be carried out in order to reuse information that may be useful in OH-FINE activities.

In addition, an extensive literature review will be undertaken to collate existing research findings. OH-FINE will develop a comprehensive database of existing resources and knowledge on organic farming practices.

All these procedures are reflected in the GA as tasks to be performed within OH-FINE. (WP2 Task 2.6. Extensive literature review; Task 2.7. Developing specific methods to prevent duplication efforts; WP5 Task 5.8. Collaboration with EIP-OG; WP6 Task 6.8. Collaboration with 10 projects; WP10 Task 10.6; WP11 Task 11.6 and WP12 Task 12.6. Collaboration, knowledge exchange and join initiatives).

3.6 The origin of the data

Data will be collected from surveys and interviews with participating producers, from measures taken in the experimental trials, from information gathered on the state of knowledge on organic farming and from the hub meetings, forums and other project activities.

The expected size will depend on the extent and the nature of the data provided and will be evaluated during the course of the project by the consortium partners.

3.7 Data utility: for whom will it be useful

Data generated by OH-FINE will be useful for:

- Partners belonging to the OH-FINE Consortium
- Farmers (conventional, pre and in-conversion and post conversion farmers)
- Agricultural advisors
- Policy makers and agriculture-related public institutions (European Commission Agriculture and Rural Development Department; national and regional authorities involved in agriculture and environment, international agencies such as FAO)
- Scientific community and agricultural research centres
- Educational/Academic Community
- Inputs suppliers and agri-food value chain operators
- Consumers and citizens

4. FAIR Data

The OH-FINE data collection will be based on 'FAIR' principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable), while always ensuring compliance with national and European ethical and legal frameworks. It is still necessary to provide more concrete details of the FAIR component, which will be addressed in the course of the OH-FINE project.

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1. Discoverability/identifiability of data (metadata provision)

In compliance with the requirements of the European Commission, all final data associated with the publications and other results of the project (including those that will not be made public in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation) will have an associated metadata document (stored as a .txt file) that provides information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s) and embargo); funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

DataCite Metadata Schema or Dublin Core metadata standards (Table 4) will be used preferably. They are both offered in such a way that they can be harvested and indexed, facilitating access and interoperability across different systems and platforms.

Table 4

Title	The name given to the resource.
Creator	The person or entity primarily responsible for creating the resource.
Subject	The topic or topics of the resource.
Description	A textual description of the resource.
Publisher	The entity responsible for making the resource available.
Contributor	An entity responsible for contributing to the creation or content of the resource.
Date	A date associated with the resource.
Type	The nature or genre of the resource.
Format	The file format, physical medium, or dimensions of the resource.

Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
Source	A related resource from which the described resource is derived.
Language	A language of the resource.
Relation	A related resource.
Coverage	The spatial or temporal topic of the resource, the spatial applicability of the resource, or the jurisdiction under which the resource is relevant.
Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

Table 4. The 15 Dublin Core elements

4.1.2. Naming conventions used

The naming convention for deliverables and for all the documents shared by the partners in the internal shared point (SACO platform) will be:

OH-FINE_WPX_Title_YYYYMMDD

Regarding other types of data, and as some repositories have their own naming conventions, the above nomenclature should be regarded as recommendation but is not compulsory

4.1.3. Persistent identifiers

Further details on the assignment and management of persistent identifiers to the data will be assessed in the course of the project and will be described in future versions of the DMP.

In order to optimize the potential of finding and re-using data, DOI (Digital Object Identifier) will be used for all data deposited in repositories.

Both Zenodo and institutional repositories that are members of DataCite (such as DIGITAL.CSIC) assign DOIs to generated data. In the case of DIGITAL.CSIC, DOI minting is also offered for other “non traditional” research outputs, such as research software, preprints and lab notebooks. In addition, DIGITAL.CSIC gives a handle identifier to each output that is uploaded onto its platform. Like the DOI, the handle is another global and permanent identifier for research outputs. In addition, Eprints IDs identifiers will be also used for data deposited in Organic Eprints.

4.1.4. Approach towards keyword

Search keywords for optimizing possibilities for reuse will be provided. Standard keywords related to agriculture, sustainability and organic agriculture that are frequently used in the scientific literature, in academic repositories, and in open data platforms such as OpenAIRE and DataCite will be used to index articles, research, and datasets.

All of the metadata elements must include the term "OH-FINE", to facilitate finding of OH-FINE data.

In addition, during the elaboration of the GA, the following keywords related to OH-FINE's activities were identified:

Organic farming, Farming Learning Community; conversion; knowledge exchange; thematic network; multi-actor; innovation; AKIS; cooperation; co-creation; cross-fertilisation; dissemination/spreading of organic farming; empowering farmers.

4.1.5. Approach for clear versioning

Filenames will include the creation date in YYYYMMDD format. Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

4.2. Making data openly accessible

4.2.1. Which data will be made openly available

Throughout the project, different types of data will be generated, some of which contain personal and financial information of the participants. According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) these data, as well as sensitive deliverables, will not be made openly accessible. In case they are used to elaborate the public reports, personal or sensitive data will be anonymized and, where necessary, encrypted before any publication or sharing.

The remaining data with scientific relevance and interest in terms of knowledge transfer related to organic production will be openly available. With respect to the ICT tool, aggregated and anonymized datasets related to user engagement and learning patterns may be made open to facilitate research and replication.

4.2.2. How the data will be made available

To provide data accessibility to all partners, a share working space was created on the SACO platform managed by CSIC as specified in the deliverable 1.1 “Project Management Plan 1”. The folder serves as a space for exchanging documents and allows for working on intermediate versions online, and has security measures in place to ensure that only consortium members have access.

With the exception of the confidential and internal management data, all scientifically-relevant data will be deposited in trusted repositories (see section 4.2.4.) Project data will be accessible to other researchers, stakeholders and the public, free of charge, with no payment or licensing restrictions limiting its use. In addition, standardised protocols will be used to enable other people or institutions to access, understand and use these data effectively.

4.2.3. What methods or software tools are needed to access the data

As stated in section 3.3, data will be published using standard file formats (txt, pdf, csv, etc.) so they will be accessible with standard tools such as Excel or Word, and any text editor or database software that can handle .csv or .json files. Data analytics may require Python or R for advanced processing.

Where data is generated during the project that requires specific software or tools, efforts will be made to ensure that these tools are open access.

4.2.4. Where data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Figure 2 shows the general data management process, from its source and raw state to the final results, including deliverables and other outputs (scientific papers, information materials on the organic conversion and post-conversion period like videos, practice abstracts or technical documents, communication and dissemination materials, etc.).

Figure 2. OH-FINE data management general procedure

For the duration of the project and for ten years after its completion, all data will be stored in the SACO platform of CSIC. At the end of the project, and in the event that the size of the files is very large (more than 30 GB), a backup will be made on at least two local devices of the CSIC coordination team.

In the case of the ICT tool, data will be stored securely on a cloud-based server compliant with GDPR regulations and access will be restricted to authorized project members with multi-factor authentication (MFA) enabled.

All final results and their metadata will be made findable and accessible through the OH-FINE website and the platform ICT Tool. Long-term access to dissemination materials on the OH-FINE website for at least 5 years post-project will be ensured. In addition, both final results and data sets will be deposited in trusted repositories. Zenodo will be the reference options because of its adherence to open science principles, long-term data preservation commitment, integration with other trusted platforms, and support for the FAIR principles. In fact, Warsaw University of Life Sciences (OH-FINE partner) has opened an institutional collection in the Zenodo repository and have the habit of using it to deposit data.

In addition, some partners are required to use the repositories offered by their own institutions (see table 5): Researchers from the Field Crops Institute (FCI, Chirpan, Bulgaria) must upload their scientific articles to the to the Bulgarian Portal for Open Science. In compliance with the latest interoperability standards the resources of this national repository are indexed by OpenAIRE. In the case of TEAGASC, it is currently in the process of developing a research data management policy. According to this policy research data should be made openly available wherever possible and if data is hosted in an external repository that a metadata record should be created on TEAGASC's upcoming platform.

In the case of CSIC researchers, CSIC's Open Access mandate obliges its researchers to deposit a copy of the data related to their scientific publications on the DIGITAL.CSIC platform. In addition, DIGITAL.CSIC data management services can be offered to partners in CSIC-led Horizon projects as long as they do not have institutional repositories to host their datasets and the principal researcher of the project requests this in writing to the management of the Scientific Information Resources for Research Unit on which DIGITAL.CSIC depends.

DIGITAL.CSIC is a repository suitable for managing and disseminating research data as it is registered in re3data, assigns DOIs to datasets and associated software, encourages the description of datasets according to DataCite recommendations and it is indexed by several research data search engines such as DataCite Search, SHARE, OpenAire and Google Dataset Search.

The term of protection of the databases in Zenodo is 20 years approximately and in DIGITAL.CSIC is 15 years from the date they are terminated or made available to the public and is subject to renewal.

Moreover, OH-FINE will integrate findings into the EU-FarmBook platform, transforming key insights into user-friendly formats, ensuring multilingual accessibility, and promoting their use for EU agriculture's sustainable development. Videos, documents and other practice-oriented material will be adapted to the standards of the platform, taking into account the limit to the file size and the files formats that are compatible with the EU-FarmBook platform. Practice abstracts and links to other OH-FINE outputs will also be published on the EU CAP Network on the dedicated OH-FINE page: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/organic-farming-innovations-network-europe_en. The EU CAP network works to optimise the flow of information about agriculture and rural policy within the EU. All practice-relevant materials will also be published on Organic Farm Knowledge. Uploads to all three platforms will be managed by FiBL-CH.

Most relevant results will be also published on Organic Eprints, an electronic, open access archive for papers related to research in organic agriculture. This archive accepts the deposit of scientific papers, conference papers and posters, theses, reports, books and book chapters, magazine articles, web products, project descriptions, and other published or unpublished documents. Instructions for OH-FINE partners on the use of this repository will be detailed in the dissemination handbook prepared by FiBL-CH.

Even when data are no longer available (because they are obsolete, change location, have been discarded or removed), metadata will remain available. Structured metadata in a standardized way and equipped with persistent identifiers (as mentioned in section 4.1.3.) allow them to be accessible regardless of the platform or system.

Table 5

Partner	Institution's requirements
CSIC	Copy of data for scientific publications in DIGITAL.CSIC
FiBL-CH	Upload publications to Organic Eprints
FCI Chirpan	Upload scientific articles to the to the Bulgarian Portal for Open Science
TEAGASC	If data is hosted on an external repository that a metadata record is made on the TEAGASC upcoming platform
SGGW	Institutional collection in the Zenodo repository (not compulsory but recommended)

Table 5. Requirements and recommendations with regard to open science and publication of their data from partner institutions

4.2.5. Embargos, intellectual property and restrictions in use

Following Horizon Europe requirements, scientific publications must be made open access immediately upon publication. There are two options: Gold open access (paid open access via the journal) or green open access (publishing the manuscript on another repository, like organic eprints or Zenodo). Prior to publication, author should share the draft with the rest of the partners, following the review process that is mentioned in D1.1 “Project Management Plan 1” and detailed in the Dissemination Handbook (D10.2. “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan 1”).

In terms of use restrictions, producers participating in the project will sign a commitment agreement in which they will give permission to the project partners to access their personal data only for purposes related to OH-FINE activities. As mentioned above, data, reports and documents containing this information subject to the GDPR will be sensitive and will be stored on the CSIC SACO platform with appropriate access and security restrictions. At this stage it is not considered necessary to have a data access committee.

4.3. Making data interoperable

4.3.1. Data and metadata vocabularies and standards to be used to facilitate interoperability

The use of standard vocabularies is contemplated in all project datasets to guarantee their interdisciplinary interoperability. The website FAIRsharing.org is being consulted for standards, datasets and policies (<https://fairsharing.org>) covering the subject “agriculture”.

Data will follow Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) and ISO/IEC 11179 standards for metadata. For structured learning data, Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) or SCORM/xAPI may be integrated, if applicable. APIs (Application Programming Interface) will be designed for interoperability with external systems if needed.

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP.

4.4. Making data re-usable

4.4.1. How the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Data will be labelled with a clear user license. In general, all relevant research data generated by the project will be reusable by third parties unless special restrictions apply (due to GDPR requirements) which will be indicated in the accompanying metadata.

For public data, the reuse of the data will be possible through the open repositories where they will be stored, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND)

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable).

4.4.2. How data reuse will be increased

All data and metadata uploaded will be trackable to any registered user (free registration to the repository). As explained above, the provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards.

Documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse (readme files with information on methodology, variable definitions, etc.) will be provided when necessary. Further details about this process will be provided in future versions of the DMP.

4.4.3. When the data will be made available for reuse

The data will be ready for reuse once published in repositories and on the OH-FINE website with the corresponding license of use.

Regarding the research data, those used to validate the results presented in scientific publications and their metadata will be deposited in the repositories as soon as possible.

The rest of relevant data generated by the project and not directly associated with any publication will also be made available, at the latest, by the end of the funded action.

4.4.4. Whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project

Public data will be available from open repositories, and therefore reusable by third parties, even after the end of the project. For confidential data, access will be compliant with GDPR which will be indicated in the accompanying metadata.

4.4.5. Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

In compliance with the GA, a long-term preservation strategy will guarantee data accessibility for at least ten years. As described above, standards and repositories that allow long-term preservation of the data will be used (Zenodo: approximately 20 years; DIGITAL.CSIC: 15 years) so this commitment will be fulfilled.

In addition, long-term access to dissemination materials on the Oh-FINE website will be ensured for at least 5 years post-project.

4.4.6. Data quality assurance processes

The research results of the OH-FINE project will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals that guarantee the quality of the information.

Regarding deliverables, the project team carries out quality control of the documents distributed according to a workflow described in the Deliverable 1.1 "Project Management Plan 1" (Dissemination Level: Sensitive), a document developed by CSIC that will be submitted in the month 5 (March 2025).

According to article 8.4.2 (Dissemination of own -including jointly owned- results) of the Consortium Agreement signed by the consortium partners, prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other partners at least 45 calendar days before the publication. The workflow for this is outlined in Deliverable 10.2 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan 1".

All educational materials will also go through a quality control process outlined in Deliverable 10.2 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan 1".

5. Other research outputs

OH-FINE project will also generate other research outputs such as an ICT tool functioning as a Decision Support System for farmers and smallholders. The

management of such outputs, in line with the FAIR principles, will be detailed on future versions of the document.

6. Allocation of resources

6.1. Cost of making OH-FINE data FAIR and ensuring long-term preservation

Free EU-funded repositories (Zenodo, EU-Farmbook, etc.) and institutional repositories are going to be used. Those institutional repositories assume the costs of storage, security and preservation.

As previously mentioned, data accessibility will be guaranteed for at least ten years. Local storage for data during and after the project on the SACO platform provided by CSIC to its staff is not estimated to be at any additional cost either.

On the other hand, partners who plan to publish scientific publications have foreseen in their budgets the potential costs of providing Gold open access (paid open access via the journal).

In the case of any unexpected costs related to data management, these will be detailed in subsequent versions of the DMP.

6.2. Responsibilities for data management in the project

Each beneficiary leading a Work Package is responsible for the supervision of data management in WP activities, provided that CSIC, as Project Coordinator is co-responsible for general coordination and supervision. Consortium partners are responsible for preparing the datasets to make the data collected FAIR within their own activities. They also have the responsibility to make sure their activities are in line with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines. To ensure that all these requirements are met, each partner has appointed a data manager who will work with the central data manager (See D1.1. Project Management Plan 1).

7. Data security

Due to the importance of protecting data that are derived from research projects from unauthorised access, it is crucial that secure measures are in place when storing both

data and information. In addition to the GDPR, the consortium partners regard privacy and data protection as a fundamental principle and hence apply a strict policy on this matter.

Data will be deposited in the SACO platform which ensures long-term preservation and curation and complies with the necessary protocols to guarantee data security and protection.

For the protection of the information the SACO service has applied the following measures with respect to the security of the installation:

- All systems associated with the service have the corporate Endpoint Detection and Response (EDR) installed.
- Web access is protected by the perimeter systems of the Security and Communications area of the CSIC General Secretariat of Informatics.
- All associated systems are controlled and monitored by Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS) of Technological Architecture.
- Blocking the uploading of content classified as malicious by the ClamAV antivirus.
- Data is transmitted in encrypted form (https).

A weekly backup of the shared folder will be made and stored locally on an IRNASA-CSIC computer protected with a password and all the security measures implemented by this institution.

The data retention policy agreed in the project states that all information should be available for 10 years after the end of the project.

With respect to Zenodo and institutional repositories such as DIGITAL.CSIC, all have security policies, long-term storage, easy access and open-access data download facilities that guarantee both data retrieval and secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.

8. Ethics

Deliverable 1.3 “Legal and Ethical report” will cover the ethics requirements in connection with the main issues of data management within the project.

9. Other issues

The DMP is a living document that will be updated periodically. The OH-FINE project comprises a multitude of very diverse activities that will also lead to the generation of very different types of data. If, during the life cycle of this data, new situations or processes arise, they will be covered in subsequent updates of the DMP.

10. Action plan

Table 6 provides a summary of the actions to perform to address unresolved issues of the present DMP. This information shall be provided in the DMP2.

Table 6

DMP component	Future actions
2.2. Data summary	<p>Define the size of each dataset</p> <p>Include data types and formats that have not been taken into account in DMP version 1 (updated table 2 and 3).</p>
3.1. Making data findable	Describe assignment and management of persistent identifiers
3.2. Making data accessible	<p>Explain whether any data has been subject to embargo (for publication or for seeking intellectual property protection for patents).</p> <p>Explain if there have been any special conditions restricting the use of the data.</p>
3.3. Making data interoperable	<p>Detail which standard vocabularies and ontologies have been used to describe the data.</p> <p>Explain if data include qualified references to other data</p> <p>In case it is unavoidable to use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, justify it and explain if generated ontologies or vocabularies will be openly published</p>

3.4. Making data re-usable	Detail if documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse (e.g., readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.) is provided.
5. Other research outputs	Detail management procedure of outputs like the ICT tool following FAIR principles.
6. Allocation of resources	Specify whether costs related to data management and allocation of resources have arisen.

Table 6. Future actions to further develop the OH-FINE DMP

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